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METHODS FOR SHIKIMIC ACID ISOLATION AND PURIFICATION

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of acronyms	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1. Shikimic acid contextualization	8
2. Materials and methods	10
2.1. Fermentation conditions	10
2.2. Pre-isolation of SA from culture broth	10
2.3. Isolation and purification by preparative ion exchange chromatography	10
2.4. Analysis by infrared spectroscopy	11
2.5. Purification by recrystallization	11
3. Results	12
3.1. Isolation and purification of shikimic acid from fermentation media.....	12
3.2. Purification of shikimic acid through recrystallization	14
3.3. Suggested step-by-step protocol.....	14
Conclusion	16
References.....	17

List of Tables

Table 1. Chemical structure of (3R,4S,5R)-3,4,5-Trihydroxycyclohex-1-ene carboxylic acid ((-)-shikimic acid) and relevant chemical aspects.	8
Table 2. Isolation and purification techniques for shikimic acid from microbial cultures.	9
Table 3. Main characteristic peaks of the isolated shikimic acid.	13
Table 4. Troubleshooting and optimization suggestions for shikimic acid isolation and purification.	15

List of Figures

Figure 1. Shikimate pathway in autotrophic cells.	8
Figure 2. Shikimic acid isolation and purification workflow.	11
Figure 3. Workflow of the purification of shikimic acid using a solvent mixture.	12
Figure 4. Shikimic acid crystals from lyophilized chromatography fractions.	12
Figure 5. FTIR spectra. A- Match between SA equipment's library and SA from the lyophilized chromatography fraction with the highest spectrum similarity (96%).	13
Figure 6. Shikimic acid recrystallization before filtration.	14

List of acronyms

ATR	Attenuated Total Reflectance
CEA	Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et Aux Énergies Alternatives
FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
SA	Shikimic Acid
RPM	Rotation per minute
UPORTO	University of Porto
WP	Work Package
w/v	Weight/volume

Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.1 establishes the framework for the sustainable extraction, isolation, and purification of shikimic acid from fermentative media within the scope of WP5, dedicated to the sustainable exploitation of heterologous bio-based systems for antibiotic adjuvant discovery. Task 5.2 - Shikimic Acid Isolation and Purification, is led by UPORTO in close collaboration with CEA, and represents a critical step in achieving the overall WP5 objective: the production of shikimic acid and its derivatives as promising adjuvant agents to combat biofilm resistance.

The *InnovAntiBiofilm* project, funded under the HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01 Twinning call, focuses on the sustainable development of adjuvant agents to enhance antibiotic efficacy against biofilm infections. The project aims to deliver innovative solutions through the synthesis of plant-based molecules and the rational development of their derivatives with improved effects. Key components of *InnovAntiBiofilm* include advanced scientific research, capacity building, talent development, networking, inclusiveness, and the enhancement of research management and administration capabilities.

The activities carried out under Task 5.2 encompass a multi-stage purification pipeline, including fermentation broth pre-treatment, ion exchange chromatography, dynamic adsorption, elution and crystallization.

This deliverable provides a detailed description of the extraction and purification workflow, along with the experimental results. The findings demonstrate a promising recovery of shikimic acid, albeit with relatively low yield, indicating opportunities for optimization in future studies. In particular, recrystallization strategies could be further evaluated to improve purity, in alignment with the sustainability principles of *InnovAntiBiofilm*.

1. Introduction

1.1. Shikimic acid contextualization

Shikimic acid (SA) is an attractive chiral building block in the pharmaceutical industry due to its carbon backbone [1]. It is a high-demand molecule in this sector. For oseltamivir production alone, it is estimated that 520 tonnes of SA each year are needed [2]. Beyond its role as a chiral building block, SA has been reported to exhibit anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antithrombotic properties [2]. In addition, within the cellular environment, SA is a precursor in the shikimate pathway (**Figure 1**), which leads to the biosynthesis of many cyclic compounds, such as aromatic amino acids or phenolic compounds [3].

Figure 1. Shikimate pathway in autotrophic cells (figure adapted from Gu et al. [3]).

Metabolic engineering efforts have been extensively carried out, especially in *Escherichia coli*, aiming SA overproduction and reducing dependence on plant-based sources, especially from *Illicium verum* (star anise), circumventing sustainable and economic hurdles. The SA content in plant-based raw materials reaches up to 8%. In contrast, studies conducted in *E. coli* through target gene manipulation have achieved production values of SA of 126.4 g/L using a 30 L fermenter with a productivity of 2.63 g/L/h and a yield of 0.5 g/g glucose [4,5].

Among the different SA isomers, (3R,4S,5R)-3,4,5-Trihydroxycyclohex-1-ene carboxylic acid has biological interest and the structure and physicochemical properties of SA are shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Chemical structure of (3R,4S,5R)-3,4,5-Trihydroxycyclohex-1-ene carboxylic acid ((-)-shikimic acid) and relevant chemical aspects [2,6].

	Physicochemical properties	Values
	Optical rotation (α)	-157° cm ³ /g.dm
	Molecular weight (M)	174.15 g/mol
	Melting point (T _m)	185-187 °C
	Maximum UV absorbance (λ)	235 nm

SA is highly soluble in water (180 g/L) and appears as white acicular crystals [2]. The purification of SA from hyperproducing microorganisms is typically carried out by isolating the compound directly from the culture broth, indicating that these hyperproducing microorganisms actively export the SA into the extracellular medium, eliminating the need for cell disruption. On the one hand, this approach avoids the need to extract SA from intracellular compounds, simplifying the purification process. On the other hand, the aqueous nature of the culture broth can make SA concentration challenging from a chemical perspective. In such cases, the most recommendable approach is to perform lyophilization of supernatants (after centrifugation to remove

solids), followed by SA dissolution in suitable organic solvents, preferably green solvents such as ethanol. If SA remains intracellular, cell disruption is required. Although this results in a more concentrated environment, it requires additional purification steps, such as filtration or chromatography, to remove intracellular content. **Table 2** gathers SA purification procedures reported in the literature from microbial sources.

Table 2. Isolation and purification techniques for shikimic acid from microbial cultures.

Microorganism	Described method	Results	Reference
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Culture broth filtration with a 20-nm membrane filter to separate cells 2. Concentration of the filtrate and fluxed at atmospheric pressure at 108 °C for 4 h 3. Acidification of the resultant aqueous mixture with sulfuric acid to pH 2.6 and filtration 4. Lyophilization of the filtrate 5. Acetone extraction of SA from the lyophilizate at room temperature with the addition of activated carbon to the extract and stirring for 15 min 6. Filtration of the extract and acetone wash. The filtrates were combined 7. Evaporation of acetone at 30–35 °C and cooling to room temperature. Seeding with a small amount of SA 8. Stored for 2–3 days at 0 °C for the precipitation of SA crystals 9. Dissolution of the previously formed crystals in ethanol and recrystallization 	SA content with 96% purity and over 80% yield.	[7]
<i>Not described</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Centrifugation of the culture broth 2. Culture broth volume reduction through boiling 3. Liquid-Liquid extraction using alcohol solvents 4. Purification through crystallization and recrystallization 	54.9% recovery, >99.5% purity.	[8]
<i>Citrobacter sp.</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Centrifugation of the culture broth at 10,000 rpm for 20 min 2. Addition of activated carbon into the supernatant and stirring uniformly at 80 °C for 60 min on the magnetic stirrer 3. Filtration with a Whatman filter paper No. 1 and concentration of the filtrate by rotary evaporation under vacuum at 60 °C 4. Desalination of the previous solution by lowering the pH to 2–3 and rest for 2 h in a water bath at 70 °C. Filtration of the resulting solution 5. Dilution of the solution with distilled water and load in an ion exchange chromatography (resin Amberlite IRA-400 Cl⁻ packed). SA elution with 2 N acetic acid 6. Combination of SA rich fractions and concentrate by rotatory vacuum evaporator at 55 °C 	Not described	[9]
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Centrifugation of the culture broth 2. Concentration of the supernatant on rotavapor until formation of a viscous mass and dissolved in methanol and followed by centrifugation 3. Drying the resultant solution in a rotavapor until the formation of a layer. The solid residue then re-dissolved in water and filtered 4. Loading of the filtrate onto an Amberlite IRA-400 (Cl⁻ form) and washing with deionized water. SA elution 	89% purity (recovery not described)	[10]

	with 25% aqueous acetic acid and concentrated on rotavapor		
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2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fermentation conditions

E. coli ATCC 25922 was employed as a model microorganism to simulate the producer strain for SA purification, while genetic engineering is being developed in the framework of Task 5.1. The culture was incubated in 200 mL at 37 °C, 200 rpm, for 72 hours, using the medium described by Li *et al.* [5]. The medium consisted of the following components: potassium phosphate ·3H₂O (7.5 g/L), ammonium sulphate (4 g/L), ammonium iron (III) citrate (0.3 g/L), magnesium sulfate (0.24 g/L), citric acid ·3H₂O (2.1 g/L), glucose (20 g/L), yeast extract (10 g/L), L-phenylalanine (0.5 g/L), L-tyrosine (0.5 g/L), L-tryptophan (0.25 g/L) and biotin (0.01 g/L). A metal ion solution was prepared separately by dissolving the following compounds in a small volume of 0.1 mM HCl: ammonium molybdate ·4H₂O (3.7 mg/L), zinc sulphate ·7H₂O (2.9 mg/L), boric acid (24.7 mg/L), copper sulfate ·5H₂O (2.5 mg/L) and manganese chloride ·4H₂O (15.8 mg/L). The metal solution and the main culture medium were then combined, followed by pH adjustment to 6.7 using 25% NH₄OH.

2.2. Pre-isolation of SA from culture broth

For experiments targeting intracellular SA, cell disruption was performed after incubation using a probe sonicator (Bandelin GM 2200). Approximately 35 mL of culture broth was placed in a 50 mL Falcon tube and subjected to sonication in an ice bath using alternating ON/OFF pulses. Specifically, the protocol consisted of two 10-second ON pulses at 100% amplitude, separated by 5-second OFF intervals to prevent overheating. Efficient cell disruption was assessed using the Live/Dead BacLight kit (Invitrogen Life Technologies, Alfacene, Portugal) as described by Afonso *et al.* [11]. In brief, SYTO 9 stains all cells green, while propidium iodide (PI) stains cells with damaged membranes red. After filtering 600 µL of the cell suspension through a 0.22 µm black polycarbonate membrane, the sample was stained with 250 µL of SYTO 9 and 50 µL of PI for 7 min in the dark. The membrane was then mounted in BacLight oil and visualized with a LEICA DMLB2 epifluorescence microscope (LEICA Microsystems) coupled with a LEICA DFC300 FX camera and a 100× oil immersion fluorescence objective. After sonication, bulk centrifugation was performed for 10 minutes at 3220 ×g for cell debris removal at room temperature. The resulting supernatant was then centrifuged using a Microsep Advance centrifugal filter (polyethersulfone membrane) with a 1 kDa cut-off (Pall Life Sciences, USA) for 90 minutes at 3220 ×g at room temperature, to retain SA in the filtrate and remove macromolecules. As the microorganism *E. coli* ATCC 25922 is not an SA hyperproducer, SA was intentionally introduced at a defined concentration (10 g/L) after macromolecule filtration to prevent enzymatic degradation of SA. The chosen concentration was based on the work of Li *et al.* [5], who reported an SA titer of 126.4 g/L with a productivity of 2.63 g/L/h. The engineering of our *E. coli* SA producer strain (Task 5.1) is being developed using this study as a baseline.

2.3. Isolation and purification by preparative ion exchange chromatography

Before column packing, 20 g of Amberlite IRA-402 resin (Cl⁻ form) was washed with 150 mL of sodium acetate (2M) in a beaker under magnetic stirring for 30 minutes at room temperature. The washed resin was then introduced into the glass column (30 x 2.5 cm), and the excess of sodium acetate was removed. To ensure complete exchange of chloride ions with acetate ions, the column was flushed twice with 100 mL of sodium acetate (2M), followed by one or two washes with 100 mL of distilled H₂O to remove residual ions. The replacement of chlorine ions by acetate ions was confirmed by the addition of silver nitrate (0.05 M) to the flushed fractions of sodium acetate as described by Xu *et al.* [12]. A volume of 100 mL of the filtrate containing SA was recirculated through the column twenty times to promote SA adsorption onto the resin and without exposing the resin to air, the filtrate after recirculation was collected and marked as the first fraction. Each

forward fraction was collected at a flow rate of 10.8 mL/min until a volume of 20 mL was reached. Sequentially, the column was rinsed with 100 mL of distilled H₂O to remove non-adsorbed species. SA was eluted with 100 mL of acetic acid (2M). A final flush with 100 mL of distilled H₂O was performed to ensure complete elution of SA from the column. Each collected fraction was lyophilized (VirTis BenchTop 6k).

So far, the isolation strategy adopted in this study considered the most challenging scenario, namely, when SA is present as an intracellular metabolite, requiring its separation from intracellular macromolecules. Accordingly, **Figure 2** illustrates the isolation workflow, which begins with cell membrane disruption by sonication, followed by bulk centrifugation to remove cell debris and prevent clogging of the following filtration device. Subsequent centrifugation using a 1 kDa cut-off filter ensured that macromolecules such as DNA and proteins were removed prior to ion exchange chromatography.

Figure 2. Shikimic acid isolation and purification workflow.

2.4. Analysis by infrared spectroscopy

The lyophilized chromatography fractions were analyzed by FTIR spectroscopy using a Spectrum TWO FT-IR (PerkinElmer) equipped with an ATR cell with a diamond crystal. Each spectrum was an average of 32 scans taken with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and within the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ range. Prior to measurement, the solids were ground with a mortar.

2.5. Purification by recrystallization

Following chromatography, the SA-containing fractions are intended to be combined and subjected to recrystallization to increase SA purity. To support this step, a parallel study was performed with stock SA to evaluate its solubility/recrystallization behavior in different solvents (ethanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, and ethyl ether). In addition, to promote crystal formation, different solvent mixtures were tested. In this approach, SA is first dissolved in ethanol at the solvent boiling temperature, after which a secondary solvent (solvent B) is gradually added at room temperature until the solution turns cloudy. At this stage, the mixture is reheated until clarity is restored and subsequently cooled (**Figure 3**). In this approach, it is important that the first solvent (ethanol) aims to specifically dissolve SA while solvent B aims to decrease the solubility of SA, achieving a hot saturated solution that will favor the formation of crystals during cooling.

Figure 3. Workflow of the purification of shikimic acid using a solvent mixture.

3. Results

3.1. Isolation and purification of shikimic acid from fermentation media

Given the ionic composition of the culture medium, anion exchange chromatography was selected as the most suitable method to isolate SA from cation and neutral species, considering a suitable target pH range. Based on the literature, SA elution was expected to occur due to the addition of acetic acid (2 M) that would lower the pH. It is important to state that the early fractions were pH > 6, which changed to pH < 3 with the presence of acetic acid. The crystals observed in the lyophilized chromatography fractions (Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada.), which were progressively formed after a couple of hours, were separately analyzed by FTIR, and some showed up to 96% spectra similarity with the standard SA spectrum available in the equipment's library (**Figure 5A**).

Figure 4. Shikimic acid crystals from lyophilized chromatography fractions (A- Small SA crystal; B- SA crystal; C- Crystal seeding).

Furthermore, **Table 3** summarizes the main absorption peaks of the FTIR spectrum and their corresponding bonds. The fractions collected with acetic acid (2 M) consistently yielded crystal formation; however, the total mass of these fractions (0.43 g) corresponded to a maximum of only 21.37% of the initial SA content due to impurity considerations. The following chromatography fractions, collected with distilled H₂O, did not indicate the presence of SA by FTIR with a total recovered mass of 0.009 g. In contrast, the total mass of the initial fractions, before SA elution and collected through distilled H₂O, amounted to 2.31 g. The FTIR spectra of those fractions were similar among each other and some are presented in **Figure 5B**, but there was no conclusive spectra match among the equipment library, indicating a mix of different compounds, either peptones, sugars or positive/neutral charge species. In addition, considering that a significant amount of SA was not degraded, it is possible that SA was not completely adsorbed into the resin due to resin saturation and shadowed in the

FTIR spectra due to a large range of different compounds.

Table 3. Main characteristic peaks of the isolated shikimic acid.

Peaks (cm-1)	Bond/Vibration mode
3500-3200	O-H stretching
1678	C=O stretching
1646	C=C stretching
1443	C-O-H bending of carboxylic acid
1268	C-O stretching of carboxylic acid
1069/1059	C-O stretching of alcohol
928	O-H out-of-plane bending of carboxylic acid
830	=C-H out of the plane bending

Figure 5. FTIR spectra. A- Match between SA equipment’s library and SA from the lyophilized chromatography fraction with the highest spectrum similarity (96%). B- Initial fractions collected by distilled H₂O.

3.2. Purification of shikimic acid through recrystallization

Literature reports have described the successful recrystallization of SA with alcohol-based solvents [13]. Consistently, among the tested solvents, only ethanol was able to dissolve SA at the solvent boiling temperature, confirming its suitability as a good recrystallization solvent. None of the other solvents dissolved SA at room temperature, nor at the respective solvent boiling temperature in suitable recrystallization conditions. For these conditions, the ratio of SA mass to solvent volume, in g/mL, must exceed 3%. **Figure 6** presents SA that was dissolved in ethanol (5% SA, w/v) at the solvent boiling temperature and subsequently cooled (first to room temperature and then to 0 °C overnight). The results suggest the formation of a solid mass, without crystals, with a liquid phase that is relevant for the portioning of potential contaminants. After filtration and drying, the solid mass corresponded to 12% SA recovery, indicating that the majority of the SA remained in the liquid phase.

Figure 6. Shikimic acid recrystallization before filtration.

To promote crystal formation, different solvent mixtures were tested. In this approach, SA is first dissolved in ethanol at the solvent's boiling temperature. Afterward, a secondary solvent (solvent B) is gradually added at room temperature until the solution becomes cloudy. At this stage, the mixture is reheated until clarity is restored and subsequently cooled (**Figure 3**). Among the B solvents tested (acetone, ethyl acetate, and *n*-heptane), only *n*-heptane induced cloudiness, enabling the recovery of 15% of an amorphous solid at a concentration of 5% SA w/v. Further procedures could be tested with other B solvents in which SA is insoluble to induce greater crystal formation. In addition, after optimizing the recrystallization procedures, further characterization analyses could be carried out using NMR spectroscopy (^1H , ^{13}C , and 2D-NMR techniques: HSQC and HMBC) to confirm the structure identification of the isolated final product.

3.3. Suggested step-by-step protocol

Based on the experiments and results obtained in Task 5.2, the following protocol may serve as a guideline for future implementations of SA isolation and purification:

Step 1. Fermentation

1. Culture in defined medium (pH 6.7, 37 °C, 200 rpm, 72 h);
2. Adjust pH if necessary.

Step 2. Cell disruption and pre-treatment

3. Apply sonication in short ON/OFF pulses (2 × 10 s, 100% amplitude, with cooling);
4. Centrifuge (3220 ×g, 10 min) to remove cell debris;
5. Use 1 kDa cut-off filtration to separate low molecular weight compounds from macromolecules.

Step 3. Ion exchange chromatography

6. Condition Amberlite IRA-402 resin with sodium acetate (2 M);
7. Recirculate sample for maximum adsorption; avoid resin overloading (critical point for yield);
8. Elute SA with 2 M acetic acid;
9. Lyophilize fractions immediately to prevent degradation.

Step 4. Recrystallization (Purification)

10. Dissolve lyophilized fractions in ethanol (≥ 5% w/v at boiling temperature);
11. Gradually add a secondary solvent (e.g., acetone, ethyl acetate, and n-heptane) until cloudiness appears;
12. Reheat to restore clarity, then cool slowly to room temperature and 0 °C overnight;
13. Collect crystals by filtration and dry.

Table 4. Troubleshooting and optimization suggestions for shikimic acid isolation and purification.

Step/Process	Potential issue	Optimization strategy
Ion Exchange Chromatography	Resin saturation leading to incomplete SA adsorption	Reduce load volumes, use multiple columns, or monitor breakthrough
Recrystallization (ethanol only)	Formation of amorphous solids instead of crystals	Add a secondary solvent (e.g., acetone, ethyl acetate, and n-heptane) to promote crystallinity
Recrystallization (yield)	Low recovery (~12%) despite purity improvement	Optimize solvent ratios, cooling rates, and seed with pure SA
Workflow sustainability	High solvent and resin use	Recycle chromatography resin, prioritize green solvents (ethanol, acetic acid)

Conclusion

The *InnovAntiBiofilm* **Task 5.2** aims to address the isolation and purification of SA from microbial fermentation. Up to this stage, a protocol for extraction and purification has been established. FTIR analyses demonstrated promising results, with spectra matches of up to 96%, indicating that the workflow is accurate, according to the expected objectives. Nevertheless, optimization steps, particularly regarding solvent selection for recrystallization, are still required to achieve higher purity and yield. Although SA was successfully isolated from the fermentation medium, the recovery yield is still low and needs to be addressed through further optimization. This task has also faced difficulties due to the complex composition of the culture medium, which is the same medium currently being used for SA synthesis in the cell-free system. Further experiments could be performed considering the recovery of the chromatography resin to increase the economic sustainability of the process.

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